

1.5 to 2.0 for magnesium and 2.5 to 3.0 for the rest of the alkaline earth metals. On addition of EDTA solution metal chelates are formed and no electro-oxidation of EDTA occurs. If a potential of 0.9-1.0 volts is applied to two platinum electrodes the residual current is registered up to the equivalence point but the current rises abruptly due to the oxidation of EDTA after the equivalence point. The titration curve has usually the shape of reverse L type. The reaction involved in the present titration is stoichiometric and quantitative with a sharp break at 1:1 ratio between elements and EDTA ions. The results obtained were within 1.0% error.

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Studies on s-Triazinyl Aryl/Alkyl Sulphones. Part I. Preparation of 4'-(2-p-Chlorophenylsulphonyl-4-Aryl/Alkyl Amino-s-Triazin-6-yl)-Aminobenzoic Acid

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P-AMINOBENZOIC acid derivatives have been found to be powerful local anaesthetic¹, important metabolite for many micro-organisms² and possess bacteriostatic property³. s-Triazine derivatives⁴⁻¹⁰ also possess therapeutic activity. With a view that more powerful therapeutic agent can be obtained, we have prepared substituted s-triazinyl aminobenzoic acid derivatives of the type I i.e., 4'-(2-p-chlorophenylsulphonyl-4-aryl/alkyl-amino-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoic acid.

(I)

Where R=arylamino, alkylamino, etc.

The first chlorine of 2, 4, 6-trichloro-s-triazin was reacted with *p*-chlorothiophenol¹¹ at 0° leading to the formation of 2, 4-dichloro-s-triazin-6-yl-*p*-chlorophenylsulphide. The second chlorine reacted with *p*-aminobenzoic acid at 30°-35° and the third chlorine at 80°-90° with different bases using dioxan as solvent. The product obtained was then oxidised to the corresponding sulphone.

Experimental

(a) **2, 4-Dichloro-s-triazin-6-yl-*p*-chlorophenylsulphide**: Cyanuric chloride (9.2 g) was dissolved in acetone (25 ml) and kept at 0°. *p*-Chlorothiophenol (7.25 g) dissolved in acetone (25 ml) was gradually added with constant stirring followed by aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (25 ml, 7%). The reaction mixture was stirred for half an hour and poured in crushed ice. The product obtained was filtered and dried; yield 13.00 g (88.90%), M. P. 116°-118°.

(b) **4'-(2-*p*-Chlorophenylthio-4-chloro-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoic acid**: *p*-Aminobenzoic acid (6.85 g) dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml, 20%) was added to the suspension of 2, 4-Dichloro-s-triazin-6-yl-*p*-chlorophenylsulphide (14.62 g) in dioxan (50 ml) at 30°-35°. The contents were stirred for an hour with the gradual addition of an aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml, 20%) and diluted with ice water. The solution thus obtained was acidified with concentrated

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF S-TRIAZINYL-*p*-CHLOROPHENYLSULPHIDES AND SULPHONES

Sr. No.	R	Sulphides		Sulphones	
		% Yield	M.P. °C	% Yield	M.P. °C
1.	Anilino	87	264-66	61	241-43
2.	<i>o</i> -Toluidino	76	150-52	57	175-77
3.	<i>m</i> -Toluidino	81	230-32	53	245-47
4.	<i>p</i> -Toluidino	83	220-22	58	250-52
5.	<i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	73	190-92	57	180-82
6.	<i>m</i> -Chloroanilino	89	260-62	64	163-65
7.	<i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	63	248-50	64	242-45
8.	<i>o</i> -Anisidino	79	240-42	53	238-40
9.	<i>p</i> -Anisidino	81	272-75	66	300 d
10.	<i>o</i> -Phenetidino	87	193-95	51	320 d
11.	Benzylamino	81	175-77	24	225 d
12.	α -Naphthylamino	67	160-62	34	260 d
13.	2,4,6-Tribromoanilino	69	198-200	84	326-28
14.	<i>p</i> -Iodoanilino	79	150-52	82	206-08
15.	<i>p</i> -Bromoanilino	86	228-30	94	360
16.	4-Acylaminoanilino	97	170-72	45	210-12
17.	<i>o</i> -Nitroanilino	72	250-52	55	235-37
18.	<i>m</i> -Nitroanilino	79	170-72	89	182-85
19.	<i>p</i> -Nitroanilino	68	185-87	88	208-10
20.	<i>o</i> -Carboxyanilino	87	189-91	82	295-97
21.	<i>m</i> -Carboxyanilino	87	305-07	50	312-14
22.	<i>p</i> -Carboxyanilino	78	252-55	81	263-65
23.	Sulphamyl	67	208-10	40	300 d
24.	4-Hydroxy-3-carboxyanilino	77	278-80	56	250 d
25.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyanilino	62	245-47	87	200 d
26.	4-Sulphoanilino	67	238-40	70	230 d
27.	α -Phenethylamino	58	164-66	86	182-85
28.	Piperidino	89	222-24	14	293-95
29.	Morpholino	77	215-17	21	300.02
30.	2-Pyridylamino	79	251-54	53	162-65
31.	<i>n</i> -Butylamino	80	176-78	53	325 d

N. B. :-All the above compounds gave correct N and S analysis

hydrochloric acid (congo red). The product obtained after the addition of aqueous sodium acetate solution (10 ml, 40%) was filtered, washed and dried. Yield 14.70 g (75%). M. P. 225°-27°.

(c) 4'-(2-*p*-Chlorophenylthio-4-aryl|alkyl-amino-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoic acid : 4'-(2-*p*-Chlorophenylthio-4-chloro-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoic acid (0.01 mole) dissolved in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (5 ml, 8%) was added to the solution of base (0.01 mole) in dioxan (25 ml) and refluxed in water bath for 1½ hr with the addition of aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml, 4%). The contents were poured into crushed ice and the clear solution so obtained was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid (congo red). The product obtained after the addition of aqueous sodium acetate solution (10 ml, 8%) was filtered, washed and dried. Physical constants of these compounds are recorded in table.

(d) 4'-(2-*p*-Chlorophenylsulphonyl-4-aryl|alkyl-amino-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoic acid : 4'-(2-*p*-chlorophenylthio-4-aryl|alkylamino-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoic acid (1 g) dissolved in acetone and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was added and warmed and then potassium permanganate solution (50 ml, 6%) was added gradually with constant stirring at room temperature till its colour persisted. The reaction mixture was kept for 3-4 hr. at 25°-30°. The solution was decolourised by passing sulphurdioxide gas. The product obtained was filtered,

dried and crystallised from ethanol. Physical constants of the compounds are recorded in Table 1.

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